

THE CONSTRUCTION OF A COLLECTIVE MEMORY OF URBAN SPACE: EXPLORING THE EXPERIENCES REPORTED BY CYCLISTS IN RECIFE - BRAZIL

William Guedes Lins Júnior
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco – Brazil
✉ william_jr@hotmail.com

Gabriela G. Jesumary
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco – Brazil
✉ gabriela.jesumary@gmail.com

Kátia Medeiros Araújo
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco – Brazil
✉ katia_araujo@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

This work explores the construction of a collective memory about the meaning and experience of the use of bicycles in the city of Recife, capital of Pernambuco - Brazil. As a demarcation of this research, a Facebook user groups' posts were analyzed. Therefore, this study focuses on the experiences and emotions that relate to processes of urban space appropriation. We used the Sociologist Maurice Halbwachs's Collective Memory theory as the main point of comparison with theoretical reasoning and empirical evidence addressed.

KEYWORDS: *Collective Memory, Experiences, Urban Space, Use of Bicycles, Bikers.*

INTRODUCTION

The recent cycling phenomenon in urban perimeters is associated with movements of international scope such as Critical Mass¹, among others. It is related, in broad terms, with the discussion of urban rights and quality of life in cities, but also has some special features in different social groups and localities where it operates.

In this paper, we explored published posts about the use of bicycles at a specific locus, the city of Recife - Pernambuco State, Brazil. These were considered instruments for exposure and construction of memories in which the bike is evoked as a depository of meaning in the process of urban space appropriation.

The Facebook group surveyed is called *Bicicletada Recife*. It is a "closed" community. Its members seem to be, predomi-

nantly, part of the middle classes² that began to render bicycle use more visible. We consider the group studied a catalyst for the recent growth of the cycling phenomenon in Recife.

We used the universe of posts published in January 2014. The authors of these publications have had their names changed, preserving the gender reference.

This work is the result of a preliminary action of a broader research project. It is the source of two dissertations undertaken by the Design Graduate Program at the Federal University of Pernambuco Program - UFPE.

If the experiences raised through memory³ can be considered the main determinant of identity (Cardoso, 2012) and the decoding of user identity can be considered a tool to support the project, it seems important to explore the memory con-

1 The Massa Crítica (Critical Mass) or "Bicicletada" (term used in many Brazilian cities, in Portugal and Mozambique) is an event and a movement that in many countries, every last Friday of the month, brings together people using human-powered vehicles, including bicycles. It has a horizontal structure and the absence of hierarchy (without leaders or statutes). The first edition of Critical Mass took place in San Francisco in 1992.

2 We adopt a concept, which is distinguished from the Marxist. It serves to "point a group that has similarities in terms of possibilities of purchase (consumption patterns) and a lifestyle composed of some common characteristics, [...], have access to varied sources of information, culture, entertainment and communication (books, television, magazines, internet, cinema, game, museum, etc.), using them" (Guimarães, 2007).

3 "Memory is the experience shifted of its point of departure in the immediate living." (Cardoso, 2012, p. 74)

structed by groups such as *Bicicletada Recife*.

In the first part of the development of this work and in order to support the discussion, we proposed topic about design and memory. Subsequently, the city of Recife is presented as a system. At the same time, Recife is considered as part of another system that the bicycle is also a part of. As a subject, the city seems to be inseparable from the construction of the identity of the *Bicicletada Recife* group. To decode the identity of this group and the meaning assigned to the bike, it is important to know about the city in which it is located. Thus, a description of some conditions and physical characteristics of the city will be given, as well as some properties that can help translate the *modus operandi* and socio-political-cultural nature of it.

We also consider that it is important to make a preliminary classification of the topics covered in the posts published in *Bicicletada Recife*, in order to show their diversity and elect the thematic focus that were made: posts that seem to portray the process of appropriation of the city through the bicycle use.

In this paper, we deal with the concept of Maurice Halbwachs' Collective Memory with the observed empirical evidence. These evidences were presented as transcription posts, in line with a proposal for a netnographic approach.

DESIGN AND MEMORY: AN APPROACH ABOUT EXPERIENCES, ARTIFACTS MEANING AND IDENTITY CONSTRUCTION

One of the Design strategies is to consider user participation in the solution process. When we try to adapt the theoretical framework presented by Löbach, this action can be carried out through the knowledge of the functions. The functions, according to the theory, are attributes that the users relate to the artifacts and that are perceived, especially during the process of using them. The functions given to artifacts are responses to the needs and desires of the user. (Löbach, 2011)

In agreement with Löbach, the needs of the individual are related to physiological prerogatives, psychological sensorial perception conditions, and "spiritual"⁴ determinants. They were associated with the Practical, Aesthetic and Symbolic functions, respectively. (Löbach, 2011)

In order to complement Löbach's proposal, another researcher was taken as a contribution. In an attempt to give effect to the theoretical paradigm adopted by Rafael Cardoso (2012), in the book *Design para um Mundo Complexo* ("Design for a Complex World"), was considered to reveal the identity of the individuals depending on the investigation of the meanings that they assign to the artifacts. To clarify this argument, we adopted "meaning" as: 1. What something is or what it expresses. 2. The importance given to something; value. While we recognize the importance of Löbach's concept on function, we chose to

4 When it allows the man to establish connections with previous experiences and sensations. (Löbach, 2001)

Need – Function Ratio Table

NEED of users	FUNCTIONS attributed to artifacts
Physiological	Practical Function
Psychological of sensorial perception	Aesthetic Function
Spiritual (evocation of past experiences)	Symbolic Function

use the term "meaning" rather than "function" in some of our placements. Therefore, despite the fact that the needs and desires of bike users can be investigated through the relation between the function and the use of bikes, the meanings can be considered as a result of a construction that is independent of the use. Through this perspective, the bike carries meaning for nonusers, although it serves no function for them.

If the meaning that individuals assign to objects is the key to decoding their identity, we can say that the experiences are the premises for the meanings that we attach to objects.

According to Cardoso, experiences are the basis for the construction of an individual's identity. There are those driven directly by the senses and others triggered by memory. This latter embodiment corresponds to indirect experiences; they are the most prevalent and important component of the definition of identity (Cardoso, 2012).

"Most of the experiences we have at our disposal are not accessed at any time by the senses, but through memory. The ability to remember what it was lived or learned and relate to the present situation is the most important mechanism for the establishment and preservation of identity of each" (Cardoso, 2012. P. 73.).

But memories, unlike a computer database, do not simply correspond to the evocation of experiences; they are much more the result of a construction (Cardoso, 2012).

"More than a simple action to recover an experience, memory is a process of reconstruction of the past by confronting the present and by comparison with other parallel experiences. Someone might remember an experience which never had - so-called 'false memory syndrome' - or you can mix your own

experiences with other people and the information acquired by indirect means (conversations, readings, audiovisual media). The memory it is more built rather than accessed [...]” (Cardoso 2012, p.75).

THE CITY, THE BIKE AND THE MEMORY OF CYCLISTS ABOUT THE CITY

We recognize the city as an artifact, since it results from human action to set the material world and, in a dimension of approach, we can understand it as a unit. It is full of functions and practical, aesthetic and symbolic meanings. In the same manner, we assume the city as a system. In this complex⁵ system, artifacts are associated with a set of natural objects and human landscape, all of them interdependent. Through these two perspectives - artifact and / or system - the city can be included in the interest of research design.

Thus, we feel the desire to evoke the memory of cycling and the meanings that can be built on it, in a way that it is considered an indivisible relation between our theme and the theme of city. Recife is subject to usage and meanings and collaborates in the construction of these memories about the bicycles.

This is a complex relationship and a special challenge for a scientific objectification. Especially when we consider a dynamic in which everything is "movement".

For the historian Rafael Cardoso, the meaning of objects is conditioned by six factors; They are related to the material conditions, "use", "environment" and "duration" and to the perception that we have of objects: the "point of view", "speech" and "experience". Cardoso argues that the concept "immovable" should not be applied to the artifacts. (2012) By transferring his argument for our discussion, we can say: both a bicycle and a historic building in a city can be said to be moving, they are mobile.

MATERIAL SITUATION OF A OBJECT	PERCEPTION THAT IS CONSTRUCTED
Use	Point of view
Environment	Speech
Duration	Experience

Finally, we agree that memory as major cause of experiences (Cardoso, 2012), should keep a dimension of the built social phenomenon (Halbwachs, 1990), and represent the confluence of individual dimensions, in which the whole becomes greater than the parts. Users and nonusers of bikes in their capacity as social actors can be understood as immersed in the contexts of culture and their relationships with oth-

5 "[...] Here shall mean a system composed of many elements, layers and structures whose interrelations condition and continually redefine the functioning of the whole." (Cardoso 2012, p. 25).

ers. The socialization of experiences, the life experiences and their emotions are evoked and shared within specific social groups. These collaborate in the construction of meanings of the group, which are kept, processed and disseminated in the face of the "mobility" of all things based on the construction of a collective memory.

RECIFE A SCENARIO FOR THE EMPOWERMENT OF CYCLISTS

Recife is the capital city of the Pernambuco State - Brazil. It is located in the Northeast region, with a warm and humid climate with an average temperature of 25 ° C (77 ° F). According to the census conducted by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) in 2010, it has a population of 1,537,704 inhabitants spread over an area of 218.50 km².

Including fourteen towns in the surroundings area (Recife Metropolitan Region), the city corresponds to the fourth largest urban agglomeration in Brazil, with 3.7 million inhabitants. It is the third most densely populated city of the country.

It has 95% of the entire value of the wealth generated from commercial activities and services. Recife estimates 74.5 years (2010) of life expectancy for its inhabitants, has an average income per capita of R\$ 1,144.26 Reais (\$ 480,53 dollars) associated with the Gini index 0.6894 (2010), which is a percentage that indicates very high inequality in income distribution. Its Municipal Human Development Index is 0.772. (2012)

One of the urban characteristics of Recife is the "verticalization", which consists of the construction of numerous large buildings contributing to the constructive densification of some of its regions. This feature, combined with others, has generated tensions between organized civil society, the private and the public sectors. The conflict revolves around issues such as quality of life, ethics and urban rights. Specifically, we highlight tensions involving the lack of roads infrastructure, urban mobility, quality and quantity of public spaces for leisure, playing sports, housing rights and the impact of car-use as the main means of transport. Recife has a high rate of violence. However, it is the Brazilian state capital city that most reduced this rate between 2000 and 2010. The Murder rate is nearly six times higher than that considered acceptable by the UN, but it is lower than that registered in cities such as Detroit and New Orleans in the United States, for example.

The Direitos Urbarnos ("Urban Rights") Group (2013) was created as a result of the organized civil society movements. In its blog, this group states that:

"Emerged from the articulation of people interested in politics and concerned with the problems of the city of Recife, from a group of people who knew each other offline, the group has been expanding through social networks and began to turn their concerns into action [...]."

Figure 1. Culture and Leisure Bike Lane, Recife – Brazil.

The Culture and Leisure bike lane⁶ was inaugurated by the government in an unprecedented way at the end of March 2013. On the one hand, in response to an expectation already present in the society, and on the other hand, attending to the goal of promoting bicycle use in the city. In turn, the cycle path was conceived as a point of intersection in the downtown area. The bike lane connects some localities in northern and southern areas of Recife to a preexistent bike path⁷, located in the beach area of the city. It works on Sundays and some holidays from 7 a.m. to 4 p.m. Although bicycle use in Recife was already in place regardless of these paths, especially for low-income workers and students, the creation of this bike lane helped encouraged this practice and the diversification of the debates about the use and meaning of bicycles among the local population.

On May 1st 2013, the AMECiclo entity (Metropolitan Association of Cyclists of Greater Recife) arises. On their website it presents itself as follows:

"The Metropolitan Association of Cyclists of Greater Recife area" - AMECiclo (2013) "has as its main axis of actions promoting the use of bicycles and democratization of public roads. In these terms, we intend to act politically through educational sporting and cultural activities in a single mosaic in which the priority is the awareness of the public nature of the urban fabric and the need to humanize it through peaceful coexistence between different modes of transport."

The AMECiclo and the Direitos Urbanos movements have been jointly outlining some dialog, presentation of ideas and integrated actions.

-
- 6 We adopt bike lane as an exclusive segregated space for cyclists and which features do not have a fixed separation. In Recife, they are isolated by mobile traffic cones.
 - 7 We adopt bike patch as an exclusive segregated space for cyclists and isolated steadily. This separation, in Recife, is basically made by concrete blocks and is located bordering the urban beaches of the south of the city.

Figure 2. Culture and Leisure Bike Lane, Recife – Brazil.

EXPLORING THE CONTENT OF POSTINGS

Looking at the records of the *Bicicletada Recife* group on Facebook, it was possible to establish an initial classification of posts, taking into consideration the arguments raised. The findings categories are reported below, though an analytical incursion into these various contributions to the *Bicicletada* website.

1. Posts that articulate and celebrate the construction of various networks about cycling in the city. The speech transcribed below illustrates the reasons that underlie the interests of so-called "pedal groups", whose objectives are considered distinct from those adopted by most participants of the *Bicicletada Recife*.

John: "about bias or pseudo-bias, I can speak for myself as an administrator of a night cycling group with more than one hundredth users. A large part of all the people who participate in pedal group is not interested in "wasting" their time protesting, arguing, seeking. Finally, they are there with the following interests: cycling, exercising, showing off, flirting, troll, etc., things like that, you know?"

The speech also records a specific conflict that is evident among the *Bicicletada Recife* participants: on the one hand, the interests of the cyclists who wish to hold a protest action, highlighting its political dimension and, second, the interests of those who seek, above all, the fun dimension.

2. Posts related to consumption associated with the practice of cycling. Several posts are related to sales and purchases of supplies and services. Some participants are looking for information about the acquisition of items associated with the practice of cycling, or about quality, advantages for safety, strength, reuse and customization of bikes.

Anna: "Why shopkeepers offer and sell expensive bikes and accessories to leisure bike lane users, who are not athletes?"

Mary: "About the shopkeepers that offer and sell expensive bikes and accessories to bike lane users who are not athletes. Well, many of these people think they are athletes. There are also people in a pedal group that ride once or twice

a week, who swear that they are athletes. Then, the shopkeeper takes advantage to make money and, honestly, I don't think it is wrong."

In this category, one can also observe the ideological perspectives of the participants, some of them conflicting. For example, the critical words related to the topic of consumption, which highlights the different interests between participants recognized as sportsmen and those who seek to cycle for fun, or think that they are professional cyclists, through the use of accessories and clothes.

The debate also highlights the efforts made by the alignment of these ideas in the group, or alternatively the search for dialogue among people interested in cycling, regardless of whether they want to be seen as social and political movements or not. This strategy ensures the possibility of building a shared patrimony of experiences and memories, despite the ideological differences.

The second speech expresses the view of some participants who recognize the traders as part of the collaborative movement. They recognize the collaboration of the world of trade and do not express prejudice against certain consumption practices, conceiving them as an important part in this field of practice.

3. Posts that criticize the initiatives related to the provision of services by municipal, state and private entities that provide bicycles and the urban infrastructure required for cycling. In the example below, still talking about "pedal groups," the author of the post points out:

John: "I do not remember writing that the "pedal" groups were the forerunners of the movement. Those who really make use of bikes expository and assiduously never represented anything to the governments, unfortunately, "(...)" and only count the number of bike paths and lanes in the outlying regions of the city. "

Through the analysis of this category of posting, we observed that participants seem to commune with the idea that it's necessary to push the State for effective actions to improve the urban infrastructure required for cycling. This goal presents itself as a common point in discourses that rest on different ideologies.

4. Posts that show self-criticism of the participants in relation to what would be a desirable social behavior in meetings. Participants of the *Bicicletada Recife* criticize the behavior of the other cyclists, exposing some practices that denounce a lack of civility in the coexistence of the group.

Amy: "Critical Mass could do more, if would show more ideal. You cannot make people believe your ideas doing what is done. In went out in the *Bicicletada*; a cyclist stopped a car... the driver asked him to move and the biker did not let him through. Then the driver drove the car against the cyclist. The car was dented and the cyclist started to kick the car. The driver was rescuing a woman who was sick. I saw! I was next to the car! Is that what we want to show?" "What impression did people go away with?"

The speech registers the participants' concern over how they are perceived by society as a result of their actions; namely, the desire for a positive image of cyclists' behavior, both internally in the group and to society at large. This reflection is consistent with the considerations of Halbwachs (1990), when the author examines the ties that bind the representations of the individual experience (substrate of the individual memory) with the collective memory.

"If these two memories are often interpenetrated; if the individual memory can confirm some of our individual mind records, rests on the collective memory, moving on it, becoming momentarily with it, it doesn't mean that it leaves its own way; and all that exterior source is gradually assimilated and incorporated into its substance. The collective memory, for the other side, involves the individual memories, but do not blend with it. It changes according to its own laws, and some individual memories sometimes penetrate it, changing the shape as they were replaced in other context that is not a personal conscience". (Halbwachs, 1990, p 54. Translated by the authors).

In the above passage, the author defines the two forms of memory that are built by people and the linkages between them. He highlights the preponderance of this second type in the constitution of broader social meanings, and as a repository with which it completes its own individual memory, that constantly appropriates and incorporates the collective memory. This construction allowed us to understand the concerns expressed in the transcript speech, related to the social representations of the group, substrate for the collective memory of the movement.

5. Posts related to (re) discovery of certain places and uses of the city. There are several postings of videos through which cyclists show emblematic places, highlighting the beauty and denouncing the evils of the city. Through these posts, cycling is constituted as a tool that enables to reveal facets of the city that are almost never displayed, providing the critical appropriation of these locations and information about them by the population, the extent to which the images are exposed to wider society through the website. In this case, it is clearly expected that individual actions contribute to the repository of collective memory, and, in turn, that repository of collective memory serves to prime basis for other individual memories.
6. Posts that highlight the dimension of the movement at local, national and international levels.

Dan: Join the Critical Mass / *Bicicletada* of January! Over 400 people have already confirmed. Get your bike (or any human-powered vehicle) and come to fight for a more humane city! (...) The "mass" is everyone, including you! Unlike many cycling "pedal" groups, a representative part of the people who participate in *Massa Crítica /Bicicletada* share the idea that we should take to the streets, using human-powered vehicles, fighting for respect, space, justice etc., since there is a pre-

dominating ideology that cities, especially the roads, were made for motorized modals. In this sense, Critical Mass/ Bicletada is a mix of protest, celebration and occupation, which takes place—anarchically—on the last Friday of each month.

Similarly, the exposure of remote images of the city contributes to potentiating its collective memory, registering the link of the group with national and international movements with similar objectives (in this case, the link with the Critical Mass movement) is also strategic as a inclusion of elements to this collective memory.

DISCUSSING THE SUBJECT

From the examination of selected posts that analyze the concept of the cycling movement, we observed more clearly: the amount of individual enjoyment among participants, their collective embeddedness at local level (political, vindicating) and also its connection with international movements with similar ideologies. This incursion has enabled us to discuss the process by which a common interest arises through the collective practice of cycling: the possibility of enjoying new locations of the city that were previously inaccessible, or with which we had no experience; the feeling that it is possible to act and intervene in the patterns of the urban environment; and the playful dimension, among others.

From the collected data, we can also infer that the context of cycling contributes to the production of a responsible perception of the city. This process is made possible both by the sharing of relationships promoted in the context of cycling events, as by the very capability of the mediation artifacts involved, especially the bicycle. The bicycle integrates the city's representations because of its relational dimension that sets in motion the prerogative of contributing to society's experiences. Its emblematic role of mobilizer sign in the social process follows this prerogative (Gell, 2011).

Much of the content available on posts refers to the claims of the conditions that allow cyclists, especially the bike lane users, the feeling of relative freedom to enjoy the city. We can say, following the suggestion of Halbwachs (1990) that the construction of emotional ties and the construction of a collective memory of urban space among this group are made possible through the emotional experiences of sharing relations in this context.

We note that there is a feedback between the fun sense of the enjoyment of cycling, the local political movement, claiming their own space for this practice, and also a larger political movement with international roots, motivated by a search for health, leisure, urban mobility, all associated with the possibility of getting to and from the city.

These aspects are highlighted in some dialogues, involving discussion about the political dimension of the Critical Mass group, in a continuous process of provocation and irony, on the one hand, and mediation and rationality, on the other.

George: Could someone explain to me what a “pedal” group is? I saw some comments here, but I not understand. It is a bus that takes people to a destination, and from there people go to their own way, to their own chosen places?

Harry: Bicletada Group means cicloactivism; and pedal groups are ciclocapitalism. They differ in their purposes and ideals.

Susan: Ready: spoke the voice of political liberalism! Indeed, lack of focus. When you buy your bike, it is already ciclocapitalism, isn't? Unless you stole a bike...

George: ... but Susan, I think he (Harry) compares someone who buys a bike because of his work and someone who buys the bike to ride. I think this concept doesn't help because it is very strong. I prefer ciclobusiness rather than ciclocapitalisms.

Analyzing the conceptualizations of *cicloativism*, *ciclocapitalism* and *ciclobusiness* for these informants, it is possible to realize, as suggested by Halbwachs, the importance of individual memories, or of the various meanings attributed to cycling by these people, in the construction of a collective image for the urban space. These constructions would also fit into Halbwachs' concept of collective memory.

Some posts, in turn, try to refine the meaning of the bicycle, drawing attention, beyond the political dimension and the appropriation of the city, also to the recreational experience and familiarity involved with the use of this artifact:

Amy: Pedal group: is a group in which people with the same intention gather to ride. They can be contrary to what many want, but they do what each one wants. We are not obligated to protest about anything! And contrary to what many think, THEY HELP TO SPREAD WHAT A BIKE IS: A MEANS TO IMPROVE HEALTH, DO SPORT AND ENJOY LEISURE. And EVERY ONE GOES THEIR YOUR OWN WAY! I think pedal groups are cool, because they are organized and fun. Moreover, they teach beginners how to pedal and people how to behave in traffic. Nobody gets to ride to get hit. We live in Brazil and not in Holland! What is this? This idea of car bureaucracy or whatever they call it is in totally disagreement ... Do you want to change Brazil? Start with yourself, encourage someone to ride, teach him a pleasant way to respect the cyclists. THAT'S WHAT THEY TEACH. See the APS, a wonderful group! It brings together people of all ages, people who have a car and who respect cyclists. To oppose the reality is a waste of time. Violence begets violence and that is what we have. I am in favor of kindness.

It is worth highlighting the above speaker's description, when he points out that pedal groups, although they have no major political claims, are "organized and fun", and contribute to the affective experience of cycling itself, in the construction of social meanings.

Other speakers point out that, apart from the idiosyncrasies that affect the relationships among participants (individu-

ally), generating difficulties by different ideologies, there is a converging motivation, synthesized in the interest of improving the urban space:

Ted: There is so much to discuss, I think we should be more united and fight for the same cause, which is in favor of making improvements in the city for more spaces for bikes!

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

To understand the constructed memory of the *Bicicletada Recife* group on Facebook, it was necessary to seek a phenomenological point of view that makes it possible to approach the city as an artifact that provides the context for this construction.

The posts of the *Bicicletada Recife* group contribute to the empirical glimpse of what would be, following Halbwachs perspective, a process through which a group of individuals who, in the dynamics of their narratives (descriptions and conflicts), reproduce a macro-collective memory of international scope about the use and meaning of the bike. This memory is permeated by the defense of sustainable and humane cities, issues related to urban mobility, urban rights and everyday practices of leisure and health. The bike artifact integrates this phenomenon as an emblematic artifact that embodies, or integrates, the desire for action of those involved.

As the initial step of a broader research project, we believe that the work displayed in this article needs improvements and insights. The issue of collecting and processing the data is still a challenge, though we intend to continue to invest in methodological netnography models.

We assumed that the recovery of the memories related to experiences and emotions in cycling would help to reveal the meanings that the members of the *Bicicletada Recife* group attach to the bike and its use. Taking into consideration the methodological user-centered-design proposal aims, we can realize, pragmatically, that the approach of the collective memory may provide support for the design and redesign of some products, systems and services related to cycling. For this, we intend to consider the relationship of memory building with the construction of the meanings we attribute to artifacts, even if we do not use them directly.

REFERENCES

- AMECiclo (2013). Retrieved Dec. 20, 2013, from <http://www.ameciclo.org/a-ameciclo>
- Cardoso, R. (2012) Design para o um mundo complexo. São Paulo, SP: Cosac Naify.
- Direitos Urbanos (2013). Retrieved Dec. 16, 2013, from <http://direitosurbanos.wordpress.com/about/>
- Gell, A. (2001) A rede de Vogel: armadilhas como obras de artes e obras de artes como armadilhas. *Revista do programa de Pós-graduação em artes visuais*, EBA - UFRJ, 175-191.
- Löbach, B. (2001) Design industrial: bases para a configuração dos produtos industriais. São Paulo: Blücher.
- Halbwachs, M. (1990) *Memória Coletiva*. São Paulo, SP: Edições Vértice, Editora Revista dos Tribunais LTDA.
- Prefeitura da Cidade do Recife. (2014). Retrieved Jan. 10, 2014, from <http://www2.recife.pe.gov.br/a-cidade/dados-estatisticos-e-indicadores-demograficos2010/#sthash.cyYsflb6.dpuf>
- Programa das Nações Unidas para o Desenvolvimento - ONU. Atlas de Desenvolvimento Humano no Brasil - Região Metropolitana do Recife. (2014). Retrieved Jan. 5, 2014, from http://www.pnud.org.br/IDH/AtlasGrandeRecife.aspx?indiceAccordion=1&li=li_AtlasRegioesMetropolitanas